

Synthesis and Characterization of Novel Methacrylate AMPS Copolymer

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Abstract

In this article, the synthesis and characterization of a new copolymer of 2-(bis(cyanomethyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (CMA2OEM)-co-2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid (AMPS) are described. The synthesis of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS consists of two parts. In the first part of the copolymer synthesis, 2-(bis(cyanomethyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (CMA2OEM) monomer was resynthesized and characterized. In the second part of the copolymer synthesis, the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS was synthesized by free radical polymerization of 2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid (AMPS) monomer in an inert atmosphere. The structure of novel oligomeric copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS has been characterized by using classical spectroscopic methods (FT-IR and ¹H-NMR). The molecular weight and polydispersity of the synthesized oligomeric copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) method.

Keywords: AMPS, CMA2OEM, copolymerization, characterization, synthesis

1. Introduction

Studies on the development of industrially usable polymers and the synthesis of polymeric materials with desired properties have increased steadily. Polymers and polymer derivatives have a widespread use due to their lower cost, high mechanical strength and flexibility, and low thermal and electrical conductivity (Sundami et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023; Shahid et al., 2025). In addition to these properties, disadvantages such as the difficulty of obtaining pure polymers and their sensitivity to heat and light create problems in the use of materials obtained from polymers (Mohanty et al., 2022; do Amaral Montanheiro et al., 2022; Jagota et al., 2025). Polymer structure and material properties are a widespread area of study (Arefin et al., 2021; Sharma et al., 2022). In order to improve the material properties of polymers, functional polymers are obtained by adding functional groups to the structure of monomers, introducing cyclic structures into the polymer structure through the monomer structure, and adding cross-linking groups to the structure of polymers. Studies on functional polymers have shown that the structure of the monomer, the structure, and the location of the substituent attached to the monomer molecule alter many properties of the monomer and the polymer (Farahbakhsh et al., 2021; Wahlen and Frey, 2021; von Vacano et al., 2023; Niu et al., 2024). Acrylate and methacrylate derivatives are among the most frequently used monomers and polymers to increase the functional properties of polymers. Acrylate and methacrylate-derived monomers and polymers have a very wide range of applications as industrial materials. Therefore, research has rapidly shifted towards this area (Corsaro et al., 2021; Kim and Shin, 2022; Kohsaka et al., 2022; Edo et al., 2025). In addition to their resistance to physical effects, acrylate and methacrylate-derived polymers can be used in a wide variety of areas, including their biologically active substances, biochemical sensor applications, drug delivery systems, soft tissue studies, and dental fillings (Robu et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022; Ismagilova et al., 2023; Podkoscielna et al., 2025). Methacrylate

derivative monomers have a wide range of applications due to their high light transmittance and good mechanical and thermal durability (Deka et al., 2022; Edo et al., 2024; Jahangari and Gramifar, 2025). Additionally, copolymer reactions are one of the most important techniques used to make systematic changes (Pirman et al., 2021). 2-Acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid (AMPS) has been widely used in recent studies due to its monomer's non-toxicity, hydrolytic stability, and low cost (Jomeh Farsangi et al., 2022; Shoukat et al., 2023). AMPS monomer molecular structure contains a hydrophilic sulfonic acid (SO₂) functional group and a nonionic amide group (Zhang et al., 2022; Poursaleh and Sepehrianazar, 2024;). It decomposes completely in the general pH range under the influence of these functional groups. Due to this feature, AMPS-based hydrogels exhibit pH-independent swelling behavior (Naeem et al., 2023). AMPS is frequently used as an additive in resin synthesis to improve their performance (Yan et al., 2025). The characteristic high water absorption capacity and electrical conductivity of poly(2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid) PAMPS enable that PAMPS and their copolymer derivatives to be used in medical applications such as defibrillator pads, ECG electrodes and similar medical equipment (Liu et al., 2023; Kong et al., 2024). In previous studies, methacrylate derivative the 2-(bis(cyanomethyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (CMA2OEM) monomer was synthesized and characterized, and its experimental-theoretical results were compared (Yalçın et al., 2019). CMA2OEM homopolymer and its copolymer with methyl methacrylate were synthesized and characterized (Çankaya, 2020). In addition, the interaction of CMA2OEM with human anti-apoptotic proteins was studied and the ability of the monomer to inhibit these proteins in silico was investigated (Sas et al., 2018). In this study, the novel copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS has been synthesized by free radical polymerization reactions. The molecular structure of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS has been determined by using FT-IR and ¹H-

NMR spectroscopic methods. All data are compatible with the literature. The molecular weight of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS were determined by gel permeation chromatography (GPC). It was oligomeric polymer.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Material for synthesis

For the synthesis of 2-(bis(cyanomethyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (CMA2OEM) monomer, iminodiacetonitrile, chloroacetyl chloride, sodium acrylate, triethylamine (Sigma) and acetonitrile were used (Yalcın et al., 2019). For the synthesis of the copolymer, CMA2OEM and 2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic (AMPS), N,N-dimethylformamide as solvent, and azobisisobutyronitrile (Sigma) as free radical initiator were used as monomers.

2.2. Synthesis of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

Figure 1. Synthesis of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

2.3. Instrumental measurements

The FT-IR spectrum of polymer was performed with a PerkinElmer Spectrum Two (UATR) IR spectrometer in the range of 4000-450 cm^{-1} . $^1\text{H-NMR}$ measurement was taken on Bruker 400 MHz in CDCl_3 as solvent with tetramethylsilane (TMS) as the internal reference. The molecular weight of the CMA2OEM-co-AMPS was determined by using gel permeation chromatography (GPC) on Waters 996 apparatus equipped with

For the synthesis of CMA2OEM-co-AMPS copolymer, firstly, two monomers, CMA2OEM (1 mmol) and AMPS (1 mmol), were dissolved in N,N-dimethylformamide solvent. The polymerization reaction was carried out under inert argon atmosphere at 70 $^\circ\text{C}$ temperature. The monomer mixture was stirred for 24 hours. Azobisisobutyronitrile (AIBAN) used as a radical initiator. The resulting copolymer was washed to remove impurities with ethyl alcohol. Synthesis of CMA2OEM-co-AMPS copolymer is shown in Figure 1. The chemical structure of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS was characterized by spectroscopic methods by FT-IR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$. Light brown solid; FT-IR (ATR, cm^{-1}): 3341-3200 (-N-H), ~ 2180 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretch), 1655 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$ ester), 1629 ($-\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide), 1549 ($-\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{NH}$), 2983 ($-\text{CH}_2$), 2935 ($-\text{CH}_3$). $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ (ppm): 7.40 (1H, s, -NH), 5.48-5.46 (2H, m, H-CH-C \equiv N), 5.67-5.50 (2H, m, -N-CH $_2$ -C), 4.85-4.65 (2H, m, -O=C-CH $_2$ -O-), 3.64-3.54 (2H, m, O=C-CH $_2$ -C-), 2.89-2.81 (H, m, -CH $_2$ -CH-C=O), 2,02 (H,s,-OH), 1.54 (s,-CH $_2$), 1.47-1.33 (3H, m, -CH $_3$).

evaporative mass detector, CHCl_3 solvent with polystyrene standards.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Spectroscopic characterization of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

3.1.1. FT-IR spectrum

The FT-IR technique is the first spectroscopic method used to identify functional groups within a molecule. FT-IR

(cm^{-1} , the most characteristic bands): 3341-3200 (N-H stretch), 2953 (C-H stretch), ~ 2180 ($\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ stretch), 1715 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ ester stretch), 1655 ($\text{C}=\text{O}$ amide stretch). The $\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{H}$ band seen in the 3000-3300 cm^{-1} range belonging to

alkenic groups in the FTIR spectrum was not observed in the copolymer. The FT-IR spectrum of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS has been shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The FT-IR spectrum of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

3.1.2. ^1H -NMR spectrum

^1H -NMR spectrum of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS following peaks appear; at 2.5 ppm for DMSO-solvent protons, 7.40 ppm for $-\text{NH}$ protons, 5.48-5.46 ppm for $\text{CH}_2-\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ protons, 4.85-4.65 ppm for $\text{O}=\text{C}-\text{O}-$

CH_2 protons, 2.89-2.81 ppm for $\text{C}-\text{CH}_2-\text{C}=\text{O}$ protons, 2.89-2.81 ppm for $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ protons and 1.54-1.33 ppm for polymer chain protons, 2.02 ppm for $-\text{OH}$ protons, 1.47-1.33 ppm for $\text{C}-\text{CH}_3$ protons. ^1H -NMR spectrum of the copolymer are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The ^1H -NMR spectrum of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

Peaks of 2-(bis(cyanomethyl)amino)-2-oxoethyl methacrylate (CMA2OEM) and 2-acrylamido-2-methylpropane sulfonic acid (AMPS) monomers vinylic protons, which are expected to be seen in the 6.5-5.5 ppm were not sighted in the ^1H -NMR spectrum of the

copolymer. This notices that polymerization has consisted.

3.2. Chromatographic characterization of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

Molecular weight and molecular weight distribution of copolymer CMA2OEM-co-

AMPS were detected by GPC. The highest molecular weight of the CMA2OEM-co-AMPS [weight-average molecular weight (M_w) = 3.612, number-average molecular weight (M_n) = 2.838] was determined, and polydispersity index (PDI) of CMA2OEM-co-

AMPS (M_w/M_n) = 1.273 was detected by GPC based on polystyrene standards. All the datas shown that CMA2OEM can be successfully copolymerized with AMPS via free radical route. GPC plots of CMA2OEM-co-AMPS are shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4. GPC curve of the copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS

4. Conclusion

In this study, the novel copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS were synthesized by the free radical chain polymerization reaction and characterized. Characterization of the copolymer were studied by FT-IR and $^1\text{H-NMR}$ spectroscopy techniques. The results obtained from spectroscopic techniques were in agreement with the literature. The chromatographic characterization of the copolymer was performed by gel permeation chromatography (GPC) method to determine the molecular weight of the polymer. It was determined that the copolymer was oligomer. The novel copolymer CMA2OEM-co-AMPS, synthesized for the first time in the literature, can be used in various material applications and will serve as a reference for similar studies.

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